

AS26556, a high-yielding red rice for semidry conditions

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In Kanyakumari district, Thovazhai and Agastheeswaram taluks have 7,000 ha of land under semidry cropping. They do not get sufficient rainfall during May-June and, because they are tail-end areas, irrigation water is generally delayed.

Rice is direct seeded when summer rains start. Local consumers prefer short bold red rice. We tested six red rice and one white rice entries under semidry conditions during the 1986 and 1987 wet seasons. The soil was a Typic Hapludalf. Rainfall received during crop growth is given in Table 1. Plot size was 4 × 2 m. Seeds were dibbled at 3-4/hill with 20 × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Sowing dates were 27 May 1986 and 23 May 1987.

AS26556 (IET5233/IR2153-26-3-5-2) had the highest yield (average 2.8 t/ha in 109 d) (Table 2). Its grain is a bold red rice. It has high panicle weight and low sterility. □

Table 1. Rainfall amount and distribution during crop growth. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-87.

Month	1986 wet season ^a		1987 wet season ^b		10 yr av rainfall (mm)
	Rainfall (mm)	Rainy days (no.)	Rainfall (mm)	Rainy days (no.)	
May	—	—	12.0	1	161
Jun	17.0	2	17.0	1	293
Jul	20.5	3	9.9	2	129
Aug	123.0	7	56.2	4	95
Sep	18.2	3	—	—	121
Total	178.7	15	95.1	8	798

^a Sowing on 27 May 1986, harvest on 18 Sep. ^b Sowing on 23 May 1987, harvest on 12 Sep.

Table 2. Performance of 7 varieties under semidry condition at Agricultural Research Station, Tirupathisaram - 629901, India. 1986 and 1987 kharif.

Culture	Grain yield (t/ha)			Duration (d)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Sterility (%)	Rice color
	1986	1987	Mean						
AS26556	2.9	2.7	2.8	109	8.0	1.4	24.2	12.8	Red
TP5106	2.8	1.8	2.3	105	10.0	0.9	21.5	17.2	Red
AS24913	2.4	1.8	2.1	112	9.0	1.3	19.6	14.4	Red
TM8089	2.8	1.4	2.1	105	9.0	1.2	24.0	13.5	Red
TKM9	1.8	2.0	1.9	105	8.0	1.1	24.1	13.7	Red
AS22954	1.7	1.5	1.6	109	9.0	1.0	26.9	15.1	Red
BG367-4	1.7	0.7	1.2	112	7.0	1.0	19.7	14.1	White
LSD (P=0.05)	0.3	0.4		3	0.9	0.2	2.7	1.4	

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Adverse soils tolerance

Path analysis of rice grain yield under saline conditions

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Rice production in saline soils could be increased considerably if salt-tolerant varieties were developed. We studied the association between yield components and grain yield under saline conditions to identify the characters that contribute to yield.

Seedlings of 19 promising lines from 7 crosses involving salt-tolerant parents were transplanted at 25 d after seeding (DAS) in a lowland field in Binh Dai

District, Mekong Delta during 1987 wet season.

Spacing was 15 × 20 cm in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-0-0 kg NPK/ha. Soil was silty clay with EC_e = 11.8 dS/m before

transplanting and 2.8 dS/m at flowering. Path coefficient analysis was used to partition the genotypic correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects.

Under saline conditions, filled grains per panicle had the largest direct effect on yield (1.092) (see table). However, its effect through sterility percentage was negative (-0.375), even though the total correlation with yield was significant.

Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on yield.^a Haugiang, Vietnam.

Variable	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length	Filled grains/panicle	Sterility percentage	1000-grain weight	Total genotypic correlation with yield
Panicle/m ²	-0.191 ^b	-0.248	-0.203	0.378	0.055	-0.209
Panicle length	-0.091	0.523 ^b	0.186	0.287	-0.054	-0.195
Filled grains/panicle	0.036	-0.089	1.092 ^b	-0.375	-0.069	0.595
Sterility percentage	-0.078	-0.162	-0.441	-0.928 ^b	-0.033	0.215
1000-grain weight	0.045	-0.121	0.320	0.130	-0.234 ^b	0.140

^a Residual effect = 0.204. ^b Direct effects. All others are indirect effects.

Sterility percentage showed a high direct effect on grain yield (0.928). Direct negative effects were observed for number of panicles/m², panicle length, and 1,000-grain weight. Other characters, such as panicles/m² did not show any direct effect on yield.

Filled grains per panicle and sterility percentage appear to be the most reliable indices for selection under saline conditions. □

Yield and yield attributes of rice cultivar Mahsuri grown at different salinity levels in farmers' fields, Khambhat taluka, Gujarat, India.

Salinity level ^a	EC (dS/m)	ESP ^b	Panicles (no./hill)	Sterility (%)	Unfilled grains hill (g)	Dry filled grains/hill (g)	Straw/hill (g)	Biological yield/hill (g)	Harvest index
Normal	1.4	0.81	15	16.9	1.66	27.14	10.3	39.1	0.69
Low	6.3	4.6	5.4	10.3	1.35	8.2	10.3	19.1	0.40
Moderate	11.8	6.9	4.8	29.7	0.45	7.1	8.83	12.1	0.33
Severe	25.6	12.0	13.2	80.6	3.4	2.7	14.6	23.1	0.11
LSD (0.05)	9.1	6.8	4.9	50.6	1.64	9.9	4.3	12.6	0.13

^aCategorized by farmers. ^bExchangeable sodium percentage.

Performance of rice cultivar Mahsuri at different salinity levels

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In villages lying between 22°24' and 22°30' N and 72°25' and 72°37' E in

Khambhat taluka, Kheda district, Gujarat, India, soil degradation caused by waterlogging has resulted in rice becoming the principal crop. This has further aggravated the salinity problem and waterlogging. Cultivable fields have been affected by salinity. We collected soil samples and rice plants (Mahsuri) from saline-affected fields to see the effect of soil degradation on the crop.

Soil analysis showed that EC values

increased from 1.4 to 25.6 dS/m. The increased salinity caused a reduction in all rice yield parameters measured (see table). The biological yield under severe soil salinity was higher than under less salinity because of the increase in straw weight per hill. Sterility increased in response to increasing salinity. Salinity decreased economic yield by 70, 74, and 90% at EC of 6.3, 11.8, and 25.6 dS/m. □

Manifestation of heterosis in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in a saline environment

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We studied the expression and magnitude of heterosis in rice in a saline environment.

Five varieties and strains were crossed during 1982:

1. NIAB RICE (NR-I)/C23-3-1
2. NR-I/IR6
3. NR-I/Jhona 349

4. Jhona 349/IR6
5. IR6/Basmati 370

The F₁ and the parents were grown in NIAB fields in Jun 1983. Six-week-old seedlings were transplanted into drainable concrete field basins (6 × 6 × 1 m). For artificial salinization, 4 commercial salts — MgCl₂, NaCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄—were mixed with soil at ratios of 1:4:5:10. Desired salinity was further achieved by infrequent irrigation with tubewell water (saline sodic). In the randomized complete block design with 4 replications, seedlings were transplanted at 1/hill and 20-cm

spacing. At least 20 plants/ replication were observed. Yield and 1,000-grain weight were recorded after drying grains to 14.0% moisture. To test the performance of F₁ hybrids, heterosis was calculated over that of the better parent.

Heterosis was variable and inconsistent not only for plant attributes but also for crosses (see table).

No heterosis was observed for number of primary branches per panicle and panicle fertility percentage in the saline environment.

The greatest heterosis for yield per

Heterosis estimates (%) in F₁ over better parents for yield and yield components of rice under salt stress.^a NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Cross	Heterosis (%)								
	Plant height	Productive tillers plant	Panicle length	Primary branches/panicle	Grains/panicle	Total florets/panicle	Panicle fertility percentage	1000-grain weight	Yield per plant
NR-I/C23-3-1	+0.6*	-17.0**	-2.2	+7.5	+44.4**	+25.9**	-2.1	-1.6	+78.0**
NR-I/IR6	+5.1*	+6.3	+7.8**	+3.3	+25.3**	+30.9**	-7.6**	+8.9**	+87.5**
NR-I/Jhona 349	+3.2*	-25.0**	-1.7	-9.2	+16.5**	+4.1	-2.8	-3.7**	-30.0**
Jhona 349/IR6	+12.4**	+54.8**	+6.9**	+9.4	0.2	+34.4**	-33.9**	+19.7**	+154.4**
IR6/Basmati 370	-13.8**	-40.8**	-4.7**	+0.9	+20.4**	+13.6**	+0.3	+11.6**	+13.9**

^a* = significant at P=0.05, ** = significant at P=0.01. pH 9.0, E_c 6.5 dS/m at 25°C, sodium adsorption ratio = 22.2.